

Evaluation of Base4NFDI

Interview guide: Evaluation of Base4NFDI

Context

The interviews are designed as explorative, semi-standardised interviews. This guide is a point of reference for topics to be addressed. However, not all aspects are likely to be covered in the same depth. The interview results will be treated confidentially and anonymised. The aggregated findings will be included in the evaluation report.

Introduction

- Information on the background and objectives of the evaluation, the content and objectives of the interview and the use of the interview results
- Brief introduction of the interview partners

Part A: Internal structure and responsibilities

- How would you describe the **area of responsibility** of your task area?
 - Do you have a particular **role** within your task area? How are the **roles distributed** in your task area?
 - Within your task area: have you made any **changes** to how you complete your tasks or fulfil/define your roles compared to how it was originally intended in the project proposal of Base4NFDI? If yes, why?
 - Do you feel you have **access** to all the **necessary resources** and information to perform your role effectively? If not, what additional support would be helpful?
 - Are there any tasks or objectives in Base4NFDI that are in your opinion not yet adequately addressed? (e.g. due to lack of financial or personnel resources)
 - Overall
 - In your task area
 - Are there **mechanisms to refine the internal structure** of Base4NFDI and its processes? (e.g. feedback mechanisms)
- To what extent are you **collaborating with other task areas** (or Service Stewards) to fulfil your tasks?
 - What topics are you discussing frequently with other task areas?
 - Do you feel that roles and responsibilities between task areas are clearly defined and communicated?
 - Are you satisfied overall with how the task areas are collaborating? Is the collaboration constructive in your opinion?
 - How would you describe the internal communication and workflow within Base4NFDI? Are there particular strengths or areas for improvement?
 - In your opinion, how well do the roles and tasks overall match the project's needs? (e.g. is any role or task missing? Are there any overlaps?)
- Which other stakeholders are you frequent in **contact** with? (e.g. consortia, certain members of consortia, sections/working groups, developer teams, TEC, consortia spokesperson)?
 - What topics are you discussing frequently with these actors/stakeholders?

- Do you find that you can help these external stakeholders/actors directly with their queries/concerns or can you refer them to a suitable contact point at Base4NFDI?
- To what extent do **strategic governance** bodies (e.g. International Advisory Board, Scientific Senate) shape the project's **overall structure** and decision-making framework?
 - How is the project structure of Base4NFDI embedded in international structures such as EOSC or the Research Data Alliance?
- To what extent are **strategic governance** bodies involved in the **operative work** of the project? What mechanisms support their integration?
 - How is the International Advisory Board involved in the processes of Base4NFDI?
 - How is the Scientific Senate and other actors from the NFDI involved in (decision-making) processes of Base4NFDI?

Part B: Process for discussing and identifying basic service candidates in the sections

- Have you been involved in **discussions about proposing a basic service** (e.g. in the sections, in a consortium etc.)?

Note: If the interviewee has not been involved in such discussions and processes, this topic can be skipped

- If so, what were the discussions about?
 - Do you know how ideas for submitting basic service proposals are generally discussed in the **sections/working groups of the sections**?
 - How are different voices and opinions are heard and reflected in the debates?
 - Are there larger "interest groups" within the sections which usually have the same perspective, or do the groups differ strongly from decision to decision?
 - To your knowledge, what relevant processes and mechanisms are in place for this? (e.g. informal discussions, regularly meetings)
 - Who is involved in the discussions and the decision-making processes?
 - How are decisions on proposing a basic service taken? (e.g. is there a voting process? If yes, please describe how it is organised.)
 - In your opinion, do the discussions in the sections and working groups reflect the needs in your consortium?
 - In your view, what criteria should be used to identify needs for basic services? (e.g. relevance for all/most/many consortia, sustainability of service solutions, easy/fast to implement)
 - Are you satisfied overall with how these discussion processes are organised?
- Do you know how the **teams that come together for a basic service proposal are initiated** (e.g. discussions in a working group)?
 - What criteria are most relevant for deciding to submit a proposal?
- How does the **Base4NFDI team support** the process for discussing and proposing basic services?
 - [Consortia/Sections only]: Do you know whom to contact at Base4NFDI if you have any queries about the proposal process?
 - Are there any aspects where more support by Base4NFDI is needed in your opinion?
 - Are there any aspects of the collaboration which can be improved?

Part C: Decision making processes

- How satisfied are you overall with the **decision-making processes** and structures for developing a basic service (e.g. voting in the TEC and in the consortia assembly, three steps for service development)?
 - Are you satisfied with how the decision-making structures are designed? (e.g. are they effective and efficient)
 - Is the decision-making process flexible enough to account for the variety of basic services that are proposed?
- How satisfied are you overall with the decisions of the **Technical Expert Committee (TEC)**?
 - Do you believe the composition of the TEC is well-balanced and adequately equipped to evaluate the technical aspects of the various proposed basic services effectively?
- Do you believe the decision-making processes in the **consortia assembly** are adequate to evaluate the basic services?
- In your opinion, do you consider the decisions made in the TEC/consortia assembly to be transparent and fair?
- [TEC only]: How does the TEC evaluate proposals for basic service candidates for each development phase? What criteria are most relevant?
 - In your opinion, are the criteria sufficient to make sure that the developed basic services are state-of-the art?
 - Are there also any strategic criteria for evaluating the basic services? (e.g. relevance for infrastructure institutions that may provide the service)

For reference: criteria for each development stage

- *Initialisation phase:*
 - *Assessment of the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of the basic service*
 - *Concept for implementation*
 - *Support of consortia*
 - *Need for technical development in NFDI*
 - *Quality and maturity*
 - *Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Risks (SWOT)*
 - *Work plan, project organization*
 - *Deliverables and milestones*
 - *Overall assessment/justification*
- *Integration phase:*
 - *Assessment of the TRL of the basic service*
 - *Evaluation of the initialisation phase*
 - *Support of consortia*
 - *Financial calculations*
 - *Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Risks (SWOT)*
 - *Work plan and project organization*

- *Integration into the (inter)national landscape (particular EOSC)*
- *Deliverables, milestones, and KPIs*
- *Interoperability with existing solutions in consortia / NFDI services*
- *Overall assessment/justification*
- *Ramping-Up:*
 - *Support of consortia*
 - *sustainability of service solution*
 - *Assessment of the TRL of the basic service*
 - *Final TRL*
- What **trade-offs** do you have to make when evaluating the basic services?
 - What role do the needs and concerns of different consortia play in the decisions?
 - How is it ensured that the proposed basic services meet the needs of the consortia? (e.g. being state-of-the-art, being interoperable with existing solutions)
- Do you have sufficient resources to fulfil your tasks in the TEC? (e.g. enough time and support)
- [TA4] To what extent do you provide feedback on the service proposals submitted?
- [Consortia spokespersons]: What are the most relevant criteria in the consortia assembly for evaluating basic services? Do you consider these criteria adequate?
- How is it ensured that the developed services are sustainable after development?
- To what extent have consortia and institutions need to commit to develop a basic service?
- [For TEC/consortia spokespersons only] How does the Base4NFDI team support you with fulfilling your tasks in the TEC/consortia assembly?
 - Is there any support missing?
 - [Non-Base4NFDI] Do you know who to contact within Base4NFDI if you have questions/concerns about the decision-making process?
- Are there any improvements to the decision-making processes of Base4NFDI you can think of?

Part D: Development / Implementation of basic services

- [Developer teams]: Can you describe the current state of your project?
- Are you satisfied overall with **the structures, processes and support** that Base4NFDI creates for the developer teams?
 - In your opinion, are the financial and personnel resources sufficient to develop basic services?
 - Are they flexible enough?
 - Is the development process flexible enough to account for specific requirements of different services?
 - Is the process for developing a basic service fast enough to deliver quick results while ensuring high-quality solutions?

- [Developer teams] How does **the Base4NFDI team support** you in the development process?
 - Is there any support missing?
- To what extent are consortia involved in the process?
 - To what extent is their feedback taken into account?
 - Do they commit to deploy the basic services?
- What activities and types of support exist/are planned to promote the basic services in the consortia? (e.g. active learning activities of consortia in e.g. trainings/workshops or passive learning activities in e.g. roadshows/presentations)
- Are there any improvements to the process of service development you can think of?

Part E: Relevance for NFDI Community

- [Consortia]: Which of the developed services do you consider useful for:
 - Base4NFDI overall
 - For your consortium
 - Your institution
- In terms of **potential user groups** of the service (e.g. institutions, consortia), what criteria must a developed service meet in your opinion to be considered a success?
- In your opinion, how well do the services offered by Base4NFDI align with the current and future needs of your consortia?
 - How well do they align with the strategic goals of your consortia?
 - [Consortia only] Do you plan to replace existing services in your consortia/institution with basic services?
- [Consortia only] Do you receive sufficient **support from the Base4NFDI team** and the **developer teams** for deploying the services in your consortia?
- What improvements or additional support do you believe Base4NFDI could offer to make their services more relevant to the consortia's work?
- When you look at all services that have been granted funding by Base4NFDI, are there any gaps, i.e. basic services that would be needed, but are not being developed?

Part F: Overall steering and strategy

- Which Base4NFDI strategy processes are you involved in?
- Are you in dialogue with other NFDI stakeholders about the project? If yes, about which aspects?
 - NFDI member institutions / (other) NFDI consortia
 - NFDI actors (e.g. Scientific Senate)
 - International actors (e.g. EOSC, RDA)
- In your opinion, are all relevant stakeholders adequately involved in the project?
- Do you think that Base4NFDI will advance / support
 - the development of structures and bodies of the NFDI?
 - the German research data infrastructure landscape in general?
 - data infrastructure user groups in the NFDI community and beyond

- the international research data infrastructure landscape (e.g. EOSC, RDA)?
- In your opinion, Is the project structure of Base4NFDI (as a joint initiative of all consortia) overall adequate to meet its goals?
- Are there any improvements to Base4NFDI you can think of?

Part G: Conclusion

- Are there any aspects you would like to mention that have not been covered in this interview?